

ONTOLOGIES MOST USED IN AGRICULTURE

Make your data interpretable and interoperable with ontologies.

ONTOLOGIES IN AG REPOSITORIES GENERIC ONTOLOGIES

ONTOLOGIES FROM GENETICS TO SOCIO-ECONOMICS

In this webpage, you will find a list of the most used ontologies in agriculture including the ontologies developed by the Ontologies Community of Practice of the CGIAR Platform for Big Data in Agriculture and its partners. It is recommended to use the following ontologies to annotate agrifood data. The schema organizes ontologies along the agri-food pathway from gene to plant, food and socio-economy. The schema is interactive with direct links to ontologies' website. It is a snapshot of the current ontologies environment and may evolve in the future. It has been adapted from a schema made by Erick Antezana, Senior Data Management Scientist at Bayer Crop Science. The webpage also offers a list of generic ontologies and thesauri and ontologies repositories.

<p>Sequences</p> <p>AGTC</p> <p>Sequence Ontology Features and attributes of biological sequence.</p>	<p>Genes</p> <p>Gene Ontology Molecular entities focused on 'small' chemical compounds.</p>	<p>Biochemical entities</p> <p>ChEBI Ontology Molecular functions, biological processes, cellular components.</p>	<p>Proteins</p> <p>Protein Ontology Protein-related entities.</p>	<p>Cell</p> <p>Cell Ontology Cell types in animals.</p> <p>Cell Behavior Ontology Multi-cell computational models.</p>
<p>Tissues and enzymes</p> <p>BRENDA tissues and enzyme Tissues, cell types and enzyme sources.</p>	<p>Anatomy</p> <p>Anatomical Entity Ontology Ontology of anatomical structures.</p> <p>Plant Ontology Plant anatomy, morphology, growth and development.</p>	<p>Species</p> <p>NCBI Taxonomy Organisms' classification and nomenclature.</p> <p>Mycobank Mycological nomenclatural novelties.</p> <p>EPPO Pest-specific information.</p>	<p>Environment</p> <p>Environment Ontology Environmental features and habitats.</p> <p>Plant Experimental Conditions Ontology Growth conditions used in plant experiments.</p>	<p>Agronomy</p> <p>Agronomy Ontology Agronomic practices, techniques and inputs.</p>
<p>Fisheries and aquaculture</p> <p>Small-scale fisheries & aquaculture ontology Fisheries and aquaculture (under development).</p>	<p>Plant phenotype</p> <p>Crop Ontology Species-specific phenotypic plant traits.</p> <p>Phenotype And Trait Ontology Phenotypic qualities.</p> <p>Trait Ontology Phenotypic traits in plants.</p>	<p>Livestock phenotype</p> <p>Animal Trait Ontology for Livestock Phenotypes of livestock in their environment.</p> <p>Phenotype And Trait Ontology Phenotypic qualities.</p>	<p>Food and nutrition</p> <p>Food Ontology Food, fodder and food processes.</p> <p>Compositional Dietary Nutrition Ontology Nutritional attributes contributing to human diet.</p>	<p>Socio economics</p> <p>SEONT Ontology for agricultural household surveys.</p>

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ONTOLOGY REPOSITORIES

- **Agroportal** offers a reference ontology repository for agronomy.
- **Ontobee** is aimed to facilitate ontology data sharing, visualization, query, integration, and analysis.
- **Ontology Look up Service of the European Bioinformatics Institute** (EBI-EMBL) provides a single point of access to the latest ontology versions.
- **FAIRsharing** is a curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies.

GENERIC ONTOLOGIES AND THESAURI

<p>AGROVOC</p> <p>Multilingual and controlled vocabulary designed to cover concepts and terminology under FAO's areas of interest.</p>	<p>CAB Thesaurus</p> <p>Controlled vocabulary for agriculture, forestry, horticulture, soil science, entomology, mycology, parasitology, veterinary medicine, nutrition, rural studies.</p>	<p>CG Core Metadata Schema</p> <p>Minimum set of elements applicable for data and publication annotation and curation across CGIAR.</p>
<p>Comparative Data Analysis Ontology (CDAO)</p> <p>Formalization of concepts and relations relevant to evolutionary comparative analysis.</p>	<p>EMBRACE Data and Methods Ontology (EDAM)</p> <p>Comprehensive ontology for bioscientific data analysis and data management.</p>	<p>GAZ</p> <p>Represents places through their names using an ontological approach to promote semantic coherence.</p>
<p>Geonames</p> <p>Covers all countries and contains over eleven million placenames.</p>	<p>National Agricultural Library's Agricultural Thesaurus and Glossary (NAL)</p> <p>Online vocabulary tools English and Spanish to select controlled vocabulary terms for subject indexing of AGRICOLA, PubAg and other databases.</p>	<p>Research Organization Registry (ROR)</p> <p>Registry of open, sustainable, usable, and unique identifiers for every research organization in the world.</p>
<p>Units of Measurement Ontology (UO)</p> <p>Ontology of units of measurements.</p>	<p>Variation Ontology (VariO)</p> <p>Ontology for standardized, systematic description of effects, consequences and mechanisms of variations.</p>	<p>VIVO Ontology</p> <p>Open-source software and an ontology for representing scholarship.</p>

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The Platform for Big Data in Agriculture harnesses the power of big data for agricultural research and development. It is one of three CGIAR research platforms and it is carried out with support from the CGIAR Trust Fund, UKAID and through bilateral funding agreements.

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